

Original article

First data on cholesterol metabolism in *Ornithodoros* argasid ticks: Molecular and functional characterization of the N-terminal domain of Niemann-Pick C1 proteins

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ABSTRACT

Cholesterol is a molecule vital for tick physiology, but ticks cannot synthesize it and rely on dietary cholesterol. Therefore, tick proteins involved in cholesterol absorption and transport, such as the Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing (NPC1) proteins, are promising targets for anti-tick vaccine development. The aim of this study was to assess the structure, function, and protective efficacy of the NPC1 orthologues identified previously in the midgut transcriptomes of argasid ticks *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata*. For this purpose, their corresponding cDNA coding sequences were cloned and sequenced, their secondary and 3D structures were predicted, and their function was evaluated through RNAi-mediated gene knockdown and *in vitro* feeding on blood supplemented with ezetimibe, which inhibits cholesterol binding by NPC1 proteins. Subsequently, the protective efficacy of a recombinant form of NPC1 from *O. moubata* (rOmNPC1) was tested in a rabbit vaccine trial. While inhibiting cholesterol absorption with ezetimibe resulted in up to 77 % mortality in adult *O. moubata*, NPC1 gene knockdown and vaccination with rOmNPC1 decreased female reproductive performance in terms of the number and fertility of laid eggs. This study presents the initial molecular and functional insights into NPC1 proteins in soft ticks and supports the hypothesis that disrupting cholesterol metabolism diminishes tick viability and reproduction, rendering Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing proteins promising targets for drugs or vaccines.

1. Introduction

Ticks represent a growing medical and veterinary concern because tick feeding cause direct damage to their hosts, but mainly because ticks are efficient vectors of numerous pathogens that cause severe diseases to wildlife, livestock, pets and humans, resulting in major economic losses worldwide (Rashid et al., 2019). Specifically, argasid ticks species of the genus *Ornithodoros* transmit the pathogens that cause Tick-borne human relapsing fever (TBRF) and African swine fever (ASF), a fatal haemorrhagic fever disease in pigs. In particular, *Ornithodoros erraticus* is the main vector of these pathogens in the Mediterranean basin and *Ornithodoros moubata* is their main vector in Africa (Arias et al., 2018; Talagrand-Reboul et al., 2018; Baños et al., 2022).

The control of tick populations has been based primarily on the use of

chemical acaricides, but these products presents serious drawbacks, including the selection of acaricide resistant tick strains, and accumulation of chemical residues in animal products and the environment (Obaid et al., 2022). Therefore, new complementary and/or alternative strategies for tick control are urgently needed, and anti-tick vaccines has been considered for years the most promising, environmentally friendly, and sustainable one (Valle and Guerrero, 2018).

The first two anti-tick vaccines, TickGARD in Australia and GAVAC in Latin America, were commercialized in the 1990s. Both vaccines were developed to combat the ixodid tick *Rhipicephalus microplus* and were based on the intestinal antigen Bm86 (de la Fuente et al., 1999; Rodríguez-Valle et al., 2012). Despite variable efficacy, the application of these vaccines has demonstrated that vaccinating hosts is a sustainable method for controlling tick populations (de la Fuente et al., 2007).

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Currently, GAVAC is the only commercialized anti-tick vaccine. Although significant research efforts have been dedicated to developing new and more effective vaccines, progress has not met expectations (Pereira et al., 2021; Ribeiro et al., 2021; Tabor, 2021).

A systematic rational search for more effective tick protective antigens would benefit from a thorough understanding of tick physiology and biology, as well as the mechanisms and molecules that regulate tick-host relationships. This requires a comprehensive analysis of the host immune response and the metabolic pathways and molecules involved throughout the parasite's life cycle (Maritz-Olivier et al., 2023).

This approach has led to investigations focusing on sequencing the transcriptomes and proteomes of tick salivary glands and midgut. The aim is twofold: (i) to enhance understanding of the genes and proteins involved in the aforementioned processes, and (ii) to characterize these proteins as candidate protective antigens in vaccinomics pipelines (Valle and Guerrero, 2018; Mans, 2020; Ribeiro and Mans, 2020; Martins et al., 2021).

The analysis of the mialomes (transcriptome and proteome of the midgut) of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* revealed a repertoire of genes and proteins that were significantly upregulated 48 h after blood feeding. These genes and proteins are predicted to play crucial roles in physiological processes associated with blood digestion, including protein digestion, carbohydrate, lipid, and iron metabolism, response to stress, endocytosis, molecular transport, and membrane traffic (Oleaga et al., 2015, 2017a, 2017b, 2018).

Among the proteins involved in lipid transport and metabolism, several transcripts encoding Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing (NPC1) proteins were identified. The NPC1 protein family is known for its role in the uptake and transport of cholesterol (Altmann et al., 2004). Cholesterol is an integral component of cellular membranes, contributing to its structural integrity and permeability. Ticks use NPC1 to take up dietary cholesterol, which is later used as a precursor of molecules that play essential roles in varied physiological processes, such as the 20-hydroxyecdysone and the antimicrobial peptide boophilin, a component of tick egg wax coat of *Rhipicephalus microplus* (Xavier et al., 2021; Maritz-Olivier et al., 2023).

While several issues related to cholesterol uptake and metabolism have been studied in insects and other parasites, information regarding ticks is scarce (Basal et al., 2005; Gondim et al., 2018). Some studies on lipid metabolism in haematophagous insects have identified sterol carrier proteins, oxysterol-binding proteins, and NPC1 expressed in the midgut epithelium. These proteins appear to be essential for growth during the early larval stages of development and are associated with dietary cholesterol (Voght et al., 2007; Godim et al., 2018). To date, the study conducted by Xavier et al. (2021) remains the sole investigation performed in ticks. This study highlights that disrupting cholesterol metabolism in *R. microplus* females hinders tick embryo development and renders eggs susceptible to bacterial colonization. Considering these adverse effects on tick fitness and reproduction, the authors suggest that molecules involved in cholesterol metabolism could serve as potential targets for tick control methods (Xavier et al., 2021).

In this study, our objective was to characterise the molecular and functional properties of the Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing proteins (NPC1) identified in the midgut transcriptomes of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*. This included assessing the phenotypic effects induced in ticks by blocking or interfering with cholesterol metabolism. To achieve this, the following investigations were conducted: (i) cloning, sequencing, and molecular analysis of NPC1 proteins in both argasids; (ii) functional analysis of NPC1 proteins through RNAi-mediated gene knockdown; and (iii) evaluating the impact of blocking cholesterol absorption in tick midguts using ezetimibe. Finally, based on the findings of the aforementioned studies, we also assessed the anti-tick protective efficacy of anti-NPC1 antibodies induced in rabbits immunised with recombinant Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing protein from *O. moubata*.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Parasite material

The specimens of *O. moubata* and *O. erraticus* used in the present study originate from two colonies maintained in the insectary of Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiology of Salamanca (IRNASA-CSIC, Salamanca, Spain). The *O. moubata* colony was established from specimens collected in Malawi, while the *O. erraticus* colony was established from specimens captured in the province of Salamanca (Spain). Both colonies are maintained in a growth chamber at 28 °C, with 85 % relative humidity and 12 h of light/darkness cycle, regularly feeding them on rabbits.

Samples of tick midgut were obtained from *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* females before blood feeding (Unfed) and at 48 h post-feeding (Fed). Ticks were dissected in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) pH 7.4 at 4 °C and midguts were rinsed in fresh PBS to remove blood and digestion waste. One half on the midgut tissues was immediately preserved in RNeasy Lysis Buffer (Qiagen) for total RNA purification, while the other half was collected in PBS for protein extraction. This process was carried out for both species in both physiological conditions, following the protocol described by Carnero-Morán et al. (2023). The protein concentration in these extracts was measured using the DC Protein Assay kit (Bio-Rad), and the samples were stored at -20 °C.

2.2. Cloning and sequencing of the NPC1 cDNAs of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*

For this purpose, we followed a standard protocol previously described in Oleaga et al. (2022), which is briefly described here.

Total RNA was extracted from midgut tissue using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen), and reverse transcription was conducted with the 1st Strand cDNA Synthesis kit (Roche). For PCR amplification, specific primers were designed with Primer3 Plus (Untergasser et al., 2007) from the nucleotide sequences of NPC1 transcripts found in the mialomes of *O. erraticus* (OeNPC1) (GenBank accession number GFWV01021875) (Oleaga et al., 2015, 2018) and *O. moubata* (OmNPC1) (GenBank accession number AY524182) (Oleaga et al., 2017a, 2017b). Primer sequences and specific PCR conditions are shown in Supplementary Table 1.

Amplicons were purified from 1 % agarose gels using the NucleoSpin Gel and PCR Clean-up kit (Macherey-Nagel) and subsequently cloned into the pSC-A sequencing vector using the StrataClone PCR Cloning kit (Stratagene) according to the manufacturer's instruction. Recombinant pSC-A clones were verified through EcoRI restriction digestion, followed by electrophoresis of the digestion products in agarose gels. Inserts were sequenced in both strands using T3 and T7 primers and their identity was confirmed by BLAST analysis (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). The corresponding amino acid sequences were obtained with the "Translate" tool in the Expasy website (<http://web.expasy.org/translate/>).

2.3. Bioinformatical analysis of NPC1 proteins

The amino acid sequences of NPC1 of *O. erraticus* (OeNPC1) and *O. moubata* (OmNPC1) were analysed *in silico* using the following tools: calculation of isoelectric point (pI) and molecular weight (MW) (https://web.expasy.org/compute_pi/); prediction of secretion signals with SignalP 4.0 (<http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/SignalP>) (Petersen et al., 2011); localization of N-glycosylation and O-glycosylation sites (<https://services.healthtech.dtu.dk/services/NetNGlyc-1.0/>; <https://services.healthtech.dtu.dk/services/NetOGlyc-4.0/>) (Gupta and Brunak, 2002); prediction of transmembrane domains with DeepTMHMM Server (<https://dtu.biolib.com/DeepTMHMM>); and identification of glycosyl-phosphatidylinositol (GPI) membrane anchor sites with NETGPI predictor (<https://services.healthtech.dtu.dk/services/NetGPI-1.1>) (Gislason et al., 2021).

Next, a BLASTp analysis was conducted to search for homologous sequences in the NCBI nr and Uniprot databases (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>, <http://www.uniprot.org/>). Homologous sequences from eight tick species with an E-value lower than 10^{-45} were aligned using ClustalW 2.1 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/jdispatcher/msa/clustalo>) (Madeira et al., 2022). Based on this alignment and including human NPC1 (NTD) and NPC1L1 (NTD) sequences as outgroups, a phylogenetic analysis was performed using the Mega 11 package (Tamura et al., 2021). The neighbor-joining method was used to construct the phylogenetic trees. Gaps were treated as pairwise deletions, and amino acid distances were calculated using the Poisson model. Branch supports were assessed through bootstrap analysis (10,000 bootstraps).

Secondary structure prediction and three-dimensional (3D) modeling were carried out using the Phyre² server (<http://www.sbg.bio.ic.ac.uk/phyre2/html/>) (Kelley et al., 2015). The 3D models were visualised using the Pymol package (<https://pymol.org/2/>). Finally, protein antigenicity was predicted using the Vaxijen portal (<http://www.ddg-pharmfac.net/vaxijen/VaxiJen/VaxiJen.html>) using the default antigenicity threshold of 0.5 for parasites (Doytchinova and Flower, 2007).

2.4. RNA interference (RNAi)-mediated gene knockdown of *OeNPC1* and *OmNPC1* and analysis of phenotypes

Gene knockdown was induced by administering batches of females from both species with a specific double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) fragment targeting the NPC1 gene of each species. The degree of silencing was calculated by measuring the NPC1 mRNA level using quantitative real-time RT-PCR (qPCR), and the phenotypic effect was assessed by feeding the dsRNA-treated specimens on rabbits

2.4.1. Synthesis of dsRNAs

For the synthesis of dsRNAs, primers T7OeNPC1_Fw and T7OeNPC1_Rv were designed to amplify a 291-nucleotide fragment of *OeNPC1* cDNA, and primers T7OmNPC1_Fw and T7OmNPC1_Rv were designed to amplify a 314-nucleotide fragment of *OmNPC1* cDNA. Additionally, a 323-nucleotide fragment of bacterial luciferase cDNA was amplified with the primers T7Luc_Fw and T7Luc_Rv, serving as an unrelated control. These primers contained the T7 promoter sequence to facilitate subsequent dsRNA synthesis (Supplementary Table 1). The amplification of NPC1 fragments from *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* was performed from cDNAs cloned into pSC-A vector (*OeNPC1*-pSCA and *OmNPC1*-pSCA), while the luciferase fragment was amplified from a commercial plasmid, pGEM-Luc Vector (Promega), according to the conditions indicated in Supplementary Table 1.

PCR products were purified from 1 % agarose gels using the NucleoSpin Gel and PCR Clean-up kit (Macherey-Nagel), precipitated with sodium acetate, and after resuspension, used as templates for the synthesis of the corresponding dsRNAs, which was carried out using the Megascript RNAi kit (Promega). The dsRNAs (*dsRNA_OeNPC1*, *dsRNA_OmNPC1*, *dsRNA_Luc*) were quantified by spectrophotometry at 260 nm using NanoDrop 2000 (Thermo Scientific), and their integrity was confirmed in 1 % agarose gels (Supplementary Fig. 1). Samples were stored at -80°C until use.

2.4.2. Injection of ticks with dsRNAs

Before dsRNAs administration, ticks were washed with sterile distilled water, alcohol, and 3 % hydrogen peroxide as described by Oleaga et al. (2022). Likewise, prior to the administration of each dsRNA, the 5 μl Hamilton syringe equipped with a 33-gauge needle was subjected to 15 successive washes with 3 % hydrogen peroxide and sterile distilled water. This protocol for washing the ticks and the Hamilton syringe was developed by Dr. Kocan's research group at Oklahoma State University (Kocan et al., 2011). It prevents the high mortality rate observed in non-washed injected ticks, likely due to contamination with agents present on the cuticle

Female ticks were immobilised dorsally on a glass slide. Each

specimen was injected with 1 μl of the corresponding dsRNA diluted in 10 mM TRIS-HCl buffer, in the lower right quadrant of the ventral side. The concentrations of the administered dsRNAs were as follows: *dsRNA_OeNPC1* = 2.7×10^9 molecules/ μl ; *dsRNA_OmNPC1* = 2.3×10^9 molecules/ μl ; *dsRNA_Luc* = 3.1×10^9 molecules/ μl .

Each dsRNA was administered to 35 females of each species. In parallel, similar batches of both species were treated only with TRIS-HCl buffer and used as control. After injection, the ticks were kept in the incubator at 28°C , 85 % relative humidity, and 12 h light/dark cycles.

2.4.3. Confirmation of gene knockdown by real-time RT-PCR (qPCR) and analysis of the phenotypic effect

The degree of silencing was individually confirmed in five specimens from each group, five days after injection, by quantifying the level of the corresponding mRNAs using qPCR. For this, female ticks were dissected, all internal tissues from each female tick were extracted together and processed for total RNA purification using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen)."

The purified RNA was treated with the Turbo DNA-free Kit (Ambion) to eliminate contaminating DNA, and cDNA synthesis was performed using the 1st Strand cDNA Synthesis kit (Roche) with the oligo-p(dT)15 primer.

The mRNA level of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* NPC1 was quantified and normalized against the level of actin mRNA, which served as a reference gene. Specific primers were designed for *O. erraticus* NPC1 (qPCR_OeNPC1_Fw, qPCR_OeNPC1_Rv), *O. moubata* NPC1 (qPCR_OmNPC1_Fw, qPCR_OmNPC1_Rv), *O. erraticus* actin (qPCR_OeACTIN_Fw, qPCR_OeACTIN_Rv), and *O. moubata* actin (OmActin_Fw, OmActin_Rv) using the Primer3Plus software. The qPCR was performed using the One Step SYBR PrimeScript RT-PCR kit (Takara) and the 7900HT Fast Real-Time System thermocycler (Applied Biosystems), following the manufacturer's instruction (Supplementary Table 1). The degree of silencing was calculated using the Ct method by comparing the gene expression levels in specimens treated with *dsRNA_OeNPC1*, *dsRNA_OmNPC1* or *dsRNA_Luc*.

The phenotypic effect of silencing on feeding, reproduction, and survival of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* was evaluated in 20 specimens from each group, which were fed on rabbits five days after dsRNA injection. After feeding, ticks were weighed to determine the amount of blood ingested, and then maintained in the culture chamber to assess survival and reproduction rates. For this purpose, each female was placed with two males in individual vials. The quantity of blood ingested, fertility, number of viable eggs deposited by females, and mortality rate were determined, with the mean and standard deviation calculated for each parameter in each group. Differences between specimens treated with *OeNPC1*-dsRNA or *OmNPC1*-dsRNA and those treated with *Luc*-dsRNA or TRIS buffer were compared using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test. The *p*-values < 0.05 were considered significant.

2.5. *In vitro* feeding on ezetimibe, an inhibitor of intestinal cholesterol absorption

As mentioned previously, the aim of this assay was to assess the effect on tick physiology of reducing or blocking the uptake of cholesterol present in the ingested host blood. For this, tick specimens were fed on blood supplemented with Ezetimibe (EZT), which is a potent inhibitor of intestinal cholesterol absorption mediated by the NPC1L1 protein and used clinically to reduce cholesterolemia (García-Calvo et al., 2005).

2.5.1. Blood preparation

The effect of EZT on *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* physiology was assessed by *in vitro* feeding on freshly obtained defibrinated ovine blood. EZT (Sigma-Aldrich) was dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, Sigma-Aldrich) to produce a stock solution of 50 mg/ml and then diluted in blood to produce a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$. For tick feeding, 450 μl of this solution were diluted in 45 ml of blood, resulting in a blood solution

with 10 µg/ml (10 ppm) of EZT and 0.02 % of DMSO. Untreated blood and blood treated only with 0.02 % DMSO were included as controls.

2.5.2. *In vitro* feeding procedure

A device akin to that described by Pérez-Sánchez and Oleaga (2017) was assembled for the *in vitro* feeding experiments. Feeding units were plastic vials (26 mm diameter) with a Parafilm membrane closing their lower side, which is in contact with blood allowing tick feeding. Feeding units were placed on 6-well plates loaded with 10 ml of blood/well, and the whole assembly was incubated at 37 °C with gentle shaking (200 rpm) on a heated shaker platform.

In this way, triplicate batches of 10 females, 15 males and 50 nymphs-3 of *O. erraticus* and 10 females, 10 males and 30 nymphs-3 of *O. moubata* were fed on treated EZT/DMSO- and DMSO-treated blood and untreated blood. Ticks were fed until repletion during 2 h. After they had detached, ticks were collected and maintained 24 h in the culture chamber at 28 °C, with 85 % relative humidity and 12 h of light/darkness cycle, until they completed emission of coxal fluid. After that, ticks were weighted to determine the amount of blood ingested and maintained in the culture chamber to assess the rates of survival, moulting (nymph-3) and reproduction (adults). For this, each female was placed with two males in individual vials, while the nymphs-3, from each batch and treatment, were placed together. After two months, the rates of mortality in every developmental stage, nymph-3 moulting and the number laid eggs and of newly hatched larvae (*O. erraticus*) or nymphs-1 (*O. moubata*) per female were measured. In *O. moubata* larvae moult directly to the nymphal stage without a bloodmeal.

The mean and standard deviation (SD) of each parameter were calculated for each group.

2.6. Production of recombinant NPC1 from *O. moubata*

As described in the Results section, the RNAi-mediated gene knockdown and blocking of intestinal cholesterol absorption slightly affected the viability of eggs laid by *O. moubata* females and significantly impacted the survival of adults of this species. Based on these results, we considered interesting to conduct a vaccination trial using the mature version of OmNPC1 (tOmNPC1) produced in recombinant form.

The recombinant tOmNPC1 was produced following standard protocols described elsewhere (Oleaga et al., 2022). Briefly, a cDNA fragment encoding a truncated form, without signal peptide, of OmNPC1 (tOmNPC1) was amplified from the previous construct OmNPC1-pSCA using specific primers designed *ad hoc* (Supplementary Table 1) that included BamHI restriction sites to aid in subcloning it into the pQE-30 expression vector (Qiagen). Recombinant plasmid tOmNPC1-pQE-30 was transformed into *Escherichia coli* M15 cells (Qiagen) and protein expression was induced with 1 mM de Isopropil β-D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) (Fisher Scientific). The expressed recombinant protein was insoluble and was therefore solubilized in 8 M Urea buffer and purified in denaturing conditions, with a final step of dialysis in PBS pH 7.4 during 24 h at 4 °C following the procedure described by Diaz-Martín et al. (2011). A yield of 146 µg of recombinant protein *per* liter of culture was obtained (Supplementary Fig. 2).

2.7. Vaccination assay with tOmNPC1

Six White New Zealand rabbits were used, randomly distributed into two groups of three rabbits *per* group. The rabbits in the vaccinated groups received three fortnightly subcutaneous doses of 100 µg/dose of tOmNPC1 in 1 ml of PBS emulsified with 1 ml of Montanide ISA 61 VG adjuvant. Rabbits in the control group were mock-immunized with PBS and adjuvant.

Every rabbit was bled before the first antigen dose (pre-immune), at 14 days after receiving the third antigen dose (immediately before tick challenge) (14 days post-immunisation, 14 d.p.i.) and at 14 days of tick feeding (28 days post-immunisation, 28 d.p.i.). Serum samples were

stored at −80 °C.

Anti-tOmNPC1 antibody titres were measured in the serum samples taken at 14 days after the third immunisation following the ELISA protocol described in Oleaga et al. (2022). The serum titre was determined as the highest dilution at which the reactivity exceeded twice the dilution of the corresponding pre-immune serum.

Next, the reactivity of immune sera against midgut protein extracts from unfed and 48-hour fed *O. moubata* and *O. erraticus* was analysed using ELISA and western blotting. For ELISA, serum and anti-rabbit IgG dilutions of 1/100 and 1/10,000, respectively, were used. The western blotting followed the method described by Carnero-Morán et al. (2023) with sera diluted to 1/50 and anti-rabbit IgG diluted to 1/2,000. The reaction was visualised using the chemiluminescent substrate Clarity™ Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad).

Once the level of induced antibodies was confirmed, homogeneous batches of 15 females, 30 males, and 50 nymphs-3 of *O. moubata*, and similar batches of *O. erraticus*, were fed on vaccinated and control rabbits. Similar to previous tests, ticks were allowed to feed for a maximum of two hours. The fed ticks were kept in the environmental chamber at 28 °C, 85 % relative humidity for 24 h to allow for coxal fluid emission. Subsequently, the ticks were weighed, and each female was placed in a plastic vial with two fed males to allow mating and reproduction. Nymphs-3 fed on the same rabbit were placed together in the same vial. All ticks were kept in the environmental chamber until the end of the experiment at three months post-infestation.

The vaccine effect was determined in fed specimens by measuring the following parameters: (i) amount of ingested blood, calculated as the weight difference before and 24 h after feeding; (ii) fertility rates of females (number of eggs per female) and egg viability rates (number of larvae or nymphs per number of eggs laid); (iii) moulting rate of nymphs-3; and (iv) mortality rates of all developmental stages.

2.8. Statistical analysis

The values of the parameters analysed in the vaccine trial, RNAi-mediated knockdown, and *in vitro* feeding on EZT-treated blood were summarised as mean ± SD per group. Differences in means between control and treated groups were compared using analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's test in the RNAi and EZT feeding assays. Differences were considered significant for a probability of error ≥ 95 % ($p \leq 0.05$). All statistical analyses were performed using SPSSv29 software (IBM).

3. Results

3.1. Sequences of Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing protein of *O. erraticus* (OeNPC1) and *O. moubata* (OmNPC1)

Previous studies on the intestinal transcriptomes of *O. moubata* and *O. erraticus* (Oleaga et al., 2017b, 2018) identified several transcripts annotated as Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing proteins, allowing us to obtain their coding sequences, design primers for subsequent cloning and expression, and perform an *in silico* analysis of the corresponding amino acid sequences.

The open reading frames (ORFs) of OmNPC1 and OeNPC1 consist of 687 bp and 666 bp, respectively, encoding two proteins of 228 and 222 amino acids with isoelectric points of 7.44 and 5.13, and molecular weights of 25.4 kDa and 24.7 kDa. Both sequences feature a signal peptide at their amino-terminal end and lack transmembrane domains, GPI anchorages, and N-glycosylation sites. Only OeNPC1 exhibited multiple O-glycosylation sites located at positions 202, 203, 206, and 212 (Fig. 1).

Conserved domain analysis revealed that the amino acid sequences of OmNPC1 and OeNPC1 possess the Niemann-Pick C1 N-terminus domain of Niemann-Pick C1 family proteins (amino acids 24-223 in OmNPC1 and 21-221 in OeNPC1) (Fig. 1). This family of proteins

O. erraticus

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atg cgg ctg acg tat tgt gca tca ttc gct ctg tgc ctt gct ctc gca tcg cag gct ttc
M R L A T Y C A S F A L C L A L A S Q A F
gct gct cga tgt gtg atg cga ggc cac tgc agc cat aac gaa gac gtc gat aaa gat att
A A R C V M R G H C S H N E D V D K D I
ccc tgt aaa gtc gac gaa gaa ccg caa gct ctg tcc gac aag caa ctc ttc gaa gaa gtc
P C K V D E E P Q A L S D K Q L F E E V
tgc ccc gat ctc gct gcg acg acg gat gtc acc tgc tgc gat gtt gaa cag ctg cag gcg
C P D L A A T T D V T C C D V E Q L Q A
ctc aaa aaa gac ttg cag caa gcc atc gat gtc ggt atg aag agg tat ccc agt tgt ctg
L K K D L Q Q A I D V G M K R Y P S C L
agg aat ttc aga aat ata ttt tgc cag ttg ctc tgc tcg ccc aag cag tcg gaa ttt gtc
R N F R N I F C Q L L C S P K Q S E F V
aaa gtg gtc gat tcg aaa gac act gac cag gac acg cag tac gtg acc aaa gta gtt tat
K V V D S K D T D Q D T Q Y V T K V V Y
gcc atc agc gag cag ttc tct aag ggt gta tac gac tcg tgc aaa aat gtt aaa gcg tac
A I S E Q F S K G V Y D S C K N V K A Y
agg gtt ctc aat cta atg acc gtc ttg tgc gga tgg tgg tgc gat cct gta aag ttc ttc
R V L N L M T V L C G W W C D P V K F F
act gtc ttg gga tca acg gcg tcg gaa gga cat tcg cct tac aag gtt gaa cca gag
T V L G S T A S E G G H S P Y K V E P E
att acg act gat gca acg atc cac gtc gct ggg acg gag ctg cgg cct ctg aat gtt gac
I T T D A T I H V A G T E L R P L N V D
gtc gtg
V V

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O. moubata

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atg cag tcg gac agt tta gtt tct gcc ttc cta tgt ttc acc ctg gtg tca acg ctg gcg
M Q S D S L V S A F L C F T L V S T L A
tct gcc agt cgt tgt gtc atg cgg ggc cac tgt gga cat gac gaa gac ctc gac aaa gct
S A S R C V M R G H C G H D E D L D K A
gtt ccc tgc aaa gtt gat cac gag ccg aag cca ctg ctg tca tcc aac tgg gac ctt ctc
V P C K V D H E P K P L L S S N W D L L
agc gaa gtc tgc cca gat atc gct gct gca ctg ggt cca gac cgc cgc acc tgt tgt gat
S E V C P D I A A A L G P D R R T C C D
gtt gaa cag ctc caa gcg ctc aag gat gat ctg cag cag cct atc gac ctc gga atg aag
V E Q L Q A L K D D L Q Q P I D L G M K
gac tct ccg cgc tgt ttg aag aac ttc cga aac atc ttt tgc caa ata ctt tgc tca ccg
D S P R C L K N F R N I F C Q I L C S P
agg cag tcg gac ttt gtc aag gta gtc act gct aaa aac acg atg ggt cta ccg tac
R Q S D F V K V V T A K N N T M G L P Y
gca acc gaa gca gtc tac gca gtg agt gaa aag ttc gcc aag gga tct tac gat tct tgt
A T E A V Y A V S E K F A K G S Y D S C
aaa aat gtc aaa gtg aag aaa att ctt aac atg atg tat ttc atg tgc gga tgg acc tgt
K N V K V K K I L N M M Y F M C G W T C
aat gca aac aag tgg ttc acg ttt ctt ggg tca aca tct tct gaa gga ggg tat tcg ccg
N A N K W F T F L G S T S S E G G Y S P
tac aaa atc gac ttc aga atc gtt gag gac tca aaa gta aaa gtg cat ggc act gat ttg
Y K I D F R I V E D S K V K V H G T D L
aag ccc atg tat gta gac ttg gcg tga
K P M Y V D L A -

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Fig. 1. Nucleotide and amino acid sequences of Niemann-Pick C1 protein N-terminal domain from *Ornithodoros erraticus* (GFV01021875, MAA46603) and *Ornithodoros moubata* (AY524182, AAS59853). In the amino acid sequences, the predicted signal peptides are underlined and the Niemann-Pick C1 N-terminus domains are shaded in grey. The O-glycosylation sites of the *O. erraticus* sequence are highlighted in red.

mediates the transport of cholesterol from the intestinal lumen to enterocytes and contains a cholesterol-binding pocket (Kwon et al., 2011).

Subsequently, after searching for orthologs using BLASTp, the amino acid sequences of OmNPC1 (GenBank accession AAS59853) and OeNPC1 (GenBank accession MAA46603), were aligned with the sequences of one species of Argasidae and seven species of Ixodidae. Overall, all tick NPC1 amino acid sequences showed high levels of conservation and similarity in their primary structure, although none of them exceeded 70 % identity (Fig. 2). The amino acid sequences of

OmNPC1 and OeNPC1 showed 59.5 % identity between them, 59.4 % and 65.8 % with *Ornithodoros turicata* sequence and ranging from 38.0 % to 45.7 % with the Ixodidae sequences. OmNPC1 showed the highest identity percentages (43.6-45.7 %) with the NPC1 sequences from the two *Rhipicephalus* species included, *R. sanguineus* (XP_037502080) and *R. microplus* (XP_037283679), the two *Dermacentor* species, *D. silvarum* (XP_037554349) and *D. andersoni* (XP_050048151), and with *Hyalomma asiaticum* (KAH6948276). Similarly, OeNPC1 showed the highest identity percentages (40.6-42.1 %) with NPC1 from *H. asiaticum*, *D. andersoni*, and *R. sanguineus* (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Multiple amino acid sequence alignment of Niemann-Pick C1 protein N-terminal domain from *Ornithodoros erraticus* (OeNPC1) (MAA46603) and *Ornithodoros moubata* (OmNPC1) (AAS59853), and from one argasid tick and seven ixodid ticks [Ot: *Ornithodoros turicata*; Ip: *Ixodes persulcatus*; Is: *Ixodes scapularis*; Da: *Dermacentor andersoni*; Ds: *Dermacentor silvarum*; Ha: *Hyalomma asiaticum*; Rs: *Rhipicephalus sanguineus*; Rm: *Rhipicephalus microplus*]. Percentages indicate the degree of identity to OeNPC1 and OmNPC1. The conserved amino acids are labelled with asterisks and the conservative and semi-conservative substitutions are labelled with two and one points, respectively. Gray background indicates amino acid conservation among all sequences. Predicted signal peptides are underlined.

Phylogenetic analysis of the nine NPC1 tick sequences (seven Ixodidae and three Argasidae) also included human NPC1(NTD) (UniProt accession O15118) and NPC1L1(NTD) (UniProt accession Q9UHC9) sequences as outgroups. Fig. 3 illustrates a phylogenetic tree with three major clades. The first clade includes the NPC1 from the two *Ixodes* species (prostrate ticks), and human NPC1(NTD). The second includes two subclades containing OmNPC1, OeNPC1, *O. turicata* sequence and two *Rhipicephalus* species (*R. microplus* and *R. sanguineus*). The third clade include human NPC1L1(NTD) as an external gene and two *Dermacentor* species (*D. andersoni* and *D. silvarum*) and *Hyalomma asiaticum* (Fig. 3).

The secondary and tertiary structures of Niemann-Pick C1 proteins N-terminal domain were highly conserved. The results of the Phyre2 analysis for OeNPC1 (MAA46603) and OmNPC1 (AAS59853) showed virtually the same model. This model mainly consists of six alpha helices and five beta sheets (Fig. 4). The 3D models obtained for the OmNPC1 and OeNPC1 sequences were both of them based on the human "niemann-pick c1 protein", with PDB codes c3gkh and c3jd8A, covering 194 residues (85 % of the sequence) and 192 residues (86 % of the

sequence) respectively, and a 100 % confidence in both cases. Fig. 4 shows the 3D models of the OeNPC1, and OmNPC1, highlighting a high degree of conservation in their tertiary structure. Similarly, the 3D models provided by Phyre2 for the eight NPC1 sequences included in the alignment showed they all have almost the same 3D structure, which is very similar to the 3D structures of OeNPC1 and OmNPC1 (Supplementary Fig. 3).

3.2. OmNPC1 and OeNPC1 gene knockdown and effect on feeding, survival and reproduction of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* specimens

The administration of dsRNA_OeNPC1 or dsRNA_OmNPC1 to females of *O. erraticus* or *O. moubata* produced, five days post-injection, an average reduction in gene expression levels of 66.6 % and 51.8 % respectively (Fig. 5). Individual expression levels in each of the ticks analysed from both species are shown in Supplementary Fig. 4. In *O. erraticus*, individual results were obtained from four ticks with reductions in gene expression levels ranging from 45 % to 79 % (Supplementary Fig 4A). In *O. moubata*, treatment with dsRNA_OmNPC1 had a

Fig. 3. Analysis of the phylogenetic relationship of Niemann-Pick C1 protein N-terminal domain of *O. erraticus* (OeNPC1) (MAA46603) and *O. moubata* (OmNPC1) (AAS59853) and its orthologues in ticks. [Ot: *Ornithodoros turicata*; Ip: *Ixodes persulcatus*; Is: *Ixodes scapularis*; Da: *Dermacentor andersoni*; Ds: *Dermacentor silvarum*; Ha: *Hyalomma asiaticum*; Rs: *Rhipicephalus sanguineus*; Rm: *Rhipicephalus microplus*]. Human NPC1(NTD) (O15118) and NPC1L1(NTD) (Q9UHC9) are included as external genes. Evolutionary distances were computed using the Poisson correction method. Branch support values (10,000 bootstraps) for the nodes are indicated.

less intense effect producing reductions in gene expression levels ranging from 37 % to 61 % in the five ticks analysed (Supplementary Fig 4B).

The effect of OeNPC1 and OmNPC1 gene knockdown on tick physiology was evaluated in 20 specimens from each group that were fed on rabbits five days post dsRNA injection. In *O. erraticus* females, treatment

with dsRNA_OeNPC1 did not affect the amount of blood ingested or fecundity (number of eggs laid) (Table 1). Only a non-significant reduction in the number of fertile eggs (% viability of eggs) was observed when compared to control groups treated with dsRNA_Luc or buffer (Table 1). Similarly, treatment with dsRNA_OmNPC1 did not affect the amount of blood ingested or fecundity (number of eggs laid) in *O. moubata* females, but induced a significant reduction in the percentage of viable eggs as compared to the control group injected with buffer (Table 1). Mortality of specimens recorded throughout the experiment after feeding (10 weeks) was zero in all groups and species.

3.3. Biological effect of feeding on a cholesterol metabolism inhibitor

As previously mentioned, ticks lack the ability to synthesize cholesterol and need to acquire it from dietary blood. The aim of this experiment was to assess the effect on tick physiology of inhibiting the absorption of cholesterol by NPC1 with EZT.

In *O. erraticus*, feeding on blood containing 10 µg/ml EZT did not affect any of the biological parameters studied (ingested blood, mortality, moulting, fecundity, and fertility) (Table 2). Additionally, the 0.02 % DMSO did not seem to produce any toxic effect on this species. On the contrary, in *O. moubata*, feeding on blood with EZT resulted in significantly higher mortality in adults compared to the control groups. Females fed on blood with EZT exhibited a 77.0 % mortality, much

Fig. 5. NPC1 gene expression knockdown in *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *O. moubata* after gene silencing by injection of dsRNA_OeNPC1 or dsRNA_OmNPC1 respectively. The graph represents the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) of four or five ticks analyzed in each group (see Supplementary Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Molecular modelling of (A) OeNPC1 (MAA46603) and (B) OmNPC1 (AAS59853).

Table 1

Phenotypic effect resulting from RNAi-mediated silencing of the NPC1 gene. Mean \pm standard deviation (SD) of the parameters measured in *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata* females injected with dsRNA_OeNPC1, dsRNA_OmNPC1, dsRNA_Luc or buffer and fed on rabbits at 5 days after injection. * $p < 0.05$ versus buffer group.

Species	Parameter	Treatment	Mean \pm SD
<i>Ornithodoros erraticus</i>	Ingested blood (mg)	dsRNA_OeNPC1	15 \pm 5.4
		dsRNA_Luc	14.9 \pm 3.4
		Buffer	15.2 \pm 2.5
	N° of eggs laid per tick	dsRNA_OeNPC1	67.4 \pm 36.5
		dsRNA_Luc	70.4 \pm 21.9
		Buffer	62.5 \pm 23.3
% Viability of eggs	dsRNA_OeNPC1	76.7 \pm 31.3	
	dsRNA_Luc	91.0 \pm 17.7	
	Buffer	89.4 \pm 15.1	
<i>Ornithodoros moubata</i>	Ingested blood (mg)	dsRNA_OmNPC1	207.6 \pm 63.2
		dsRNA_Luc	244.5 \pm 107.5
		Buffer	183.6 \pm 70.2
		dsRNA_OmNPC1	217.5 \pm 66.8
	N° of eggs laid per tick	dsRNA_Luc	227.1 \pm 74.2
		Buffer	210.8 \pm 78.1
	% Viability of eggs	dsRNA_OmNPC1	78.5 \pm 27.5*
		dsRNA_Luc	88.3 \pm 14.08
		Buffer	92.3 \pm 11.1

higher than those of females fed on blood or blood with DMSO, which were 26.7 % and 31.3 % respectively. In males, the effect was similar: males fed on blood with EZT showed a 68.7 % mortality while males fed on blood or blood with DMSO showed 29.3 % and 21.0 % mortality, respectively (Table 2). Adult mortality was recorded over the 2-month duration of the experiment, although most mortalities occurred between 48 h and 10 days post-feeding.

The *O. moubata* nymphs-3 fed on blood with EZT and blood with DMSO ingested significant lower amount of blood than nymphs-3 fed on blood only. Accordingly, this reduced blood intake could not be attributed to a specific effect of EZT but perhaps to some toxicity of the DMSO for the immature stages of this species (Table 2)

3.4. Vaccination assay

The results obtained in the previous tests for *O. moubata* prompted us to conduct a preliminary vaccination trial with recombinant tOmNPC1. The objective of the assay was to evaluate whether immunizing rabbits with tOmNPC1 would induce protective immune responses.

Immunization with recombinant tOmNPC1 induced a robust humoral response in all rabbits, reaching antibody titres higher than 1/12,000 at 14 days post-immunization (Supplementary Fig. 5), which were maintained for at least up to 28 days post-immunization (Fig. 6). In ELISA, the anti-tOmNPC1 antibodies did not react with protein extracts from the midgut of either *O. moubata* or *O. erraticus*, but show higher background reactivity to protein extracts from fed ticks, much likely due to unspecific binding to rabbit immunoglobulins ingested in the diet and present in the intestinal extracts (Fig. 6). Rabbits from control group showed antibody levels similar to those of preimmune sera (before 1st antigen dose) from vaccinated rabbits (data not show).

The reactivity of anti-tOmNPC1 antibodies with native NPC1 present in midgut extracts was also analysed by western blotting (Fig. 7). Figs. 7A and 7B show the band patterns of protein extracts from *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* midguts obtained from unfed and 48 h post-fed females stained with silver and Coomassie blue. Pre-immune serum only revealed bands corresponding to rabbit IgG heavy chain ingested with host blood (Fig. 7C), whereas the anti-tOmNPC1 serum also

Table 2

Effect of feeding on ezetimibe-supplemented blood on the physiology of adult and nymphs-3 of *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata* ticks. Ticks (male, female and nymph-3) were artificially fed on ovine blood only (Blood group), ovine blood containing 0.02 % DMSO (DMSO group) or on ovine blood containing 0.02 % DMSO and 10 μ g/ml Ezetimibe (EZT group). The experiment was performed in triplicate. The results are shown as mean \pm standard deviation for each tick group. Means were compared between ticks fed on EZT, DMSO and Blood groups by one-way ANOVA. Values $p < 0.05$ were considered significant (** $p < 0.01$).

Parameter	Developmental stage	Blood group	DMSO group	EZT group
<i>Ornithodoros erraticus</i>				
Ingested blood (mg)	Male	1.7 \pm 0.3	1.4 \pm 0.5	1.8 \pm 0.4
	Female	10.6 \pm 3.0	10.6 \pm 1.4	10.1 \pm 1.0
	Nymph-3	2.2 \pm 0.6	1.8 \pm 0.1	2.2 \pm 0.4
Mortality (%)	Male	0	0	0
	Female	0	0	0
	Nymph-3	0	0	2.3 \pm 3.5
Moulting (%)	Nymph-3	64.5 \pm 6.7	68.9 \pm 11.9	87.1 \pm 10.5
		N° of eggs laid per tick	Female	34.5 \pm 20.0
Viability of eggs (%)	Female	97.7 \pm 4.0	86.8 \pm 30.1	79.3 \pm 32.3
		<i>Ornithodoros moubata</i>		
Ingested blood (mg)	Male	37.9 \pm 1.0	33.1 \pm 3.7	35.0 \pm 11.2
	Female	123.2 \pm 20.9	112.6 \pm 8.9	136.9 \pm 18.3
	Nymph-3	3.6 \pm 0.9	2.2 \pm 0.5**	2.3 \pm 0.4**
Mortality (%)	Male	29.3 \pm 6.4	21.0 \pm 1.2	68.7 \pm 9.5**
	Female	26.7 \pm 25.2	31.3 \pm 14.4	77.0 \pm 17.9**
	Nymph-3	20.3 \pm 13.5	6.3 \pm 9.7	14.5 \pm 2.8
Moulting (%)	Nymph-3	64.0 \pm 6.5	76.4 \pm 11.7	62.8 \pm 8.4
		N° of eggs laid per tick	Female	80.5 \pm 31.9
Viability of eggs (%)	Female	86.9 \pm 8.2	68.9 \pm 22.2	69.7 \pm 36.7

recognised in *O. moubata* intestinal extracts two bands compatible with the molecular weight of native NPC1 (approximately 25 kDa). These bands were not revealed on the *O. erraticus* midgut extracts (Fig. 7D).

The vaccine effect was evaluated by feeding 30 males, 15 females, and 50 nymphs-3 of *O. moubata* and equivalent batches of *O. erraticus* on every control (R1, R2, R3) and immunised (R4, R5, R6) rabbits. The amount of blood ingested, oviposition, number of viable eggs deposited by females, moulting rates of nymphs-3, and mortality rates of all developmental stages were determined.

In *O. moubata*, no significant differences were observed between tick fed on vaccinated and control groups for any of the parameters analysed. Only a slight reduction without statistical significance in the number of eggs laid by females fed on vaccinated versus control rabbits was observed (194.86 eggs/female and 229.25 eggs/female, respectively) (Table 3). Similarly, in *O. erraticus*, the immune response induced by tOmNPC1 had no protective effect. No differences were observed between ticks fed on control and vaccinated rabbits for any of the parameters analysed and in any developmental stage (Table 3).

Fig. 6. IgG antibody response in rabbits immunized with recombinant tOmNPC1. Sera were taken before immunization (preimmune), 14 days post-immunization (14 d.p.i.) and 28 days post-immunization (28 d.p.i.). Midgut_U and Midgut_F are midgut protein extracts from unfed and fed ticks, respectively.

Fig. 7. Western blot analyses for native OmNPC1 and OeNPC1 in midgut protein extract. Coomassie blue (A) and Silver (B) stained 12 % polyacrylamide gels. Antigens revealed in the midgut protein extracts from *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *O. moubata* by the preimmune sera (C) and sera from rabbits immunised with the tOmNPC1 recombinant protein (D). U, midgut protein extract of unfed ticks; F, midgut protein extract of fed ticks. Arrow: OmNPC1 native protein in the extracts. Asterisks: IgG heavy chain from the rabbit host ingested with blood meal.

4. Discussion

Cholesterol is an essential component of cell membranes in all living beings. Besides its structural functions, it is critical for cellular growth and development, functional dynamics of membranes, signal

transduction between cells and as a precursor in the synthesis of hormones and other biomolecules playing key functions in varied physiological processes (Bansal et al., 2005; Kwon et al., 2011).

Vertebrate cells can synthesize cholesterol, but arthropods and other parasite organisms, including ticks, lack this capability and thus depend

Table 3

Mean \pm standard deviation of the parameters measured in *Ornithodoros moubata* and *Ornithodoros erraticus* ticks fed on control rabbits and on rabbits vaccinated with tOmNPC1 recombinant.

Species	Parameter	Developmental stage	Control group	tOmNPC1
<i>Ornithodoros moubata</i>	Ingested blood (mg)	Males	32.62 \pm 1.66	33.20 \pm 3.38
		Females	233.58 \pm 12.43	198.05 \pm 23.53
		Nymphs-3	18.00 \pm 1.46	19.60 \pm 1.62
	Mortality (%)	Males	15.025 \pm 8.98	3.53 \pm 2.82
		Females	4.44 \pm 3.14	11.11 \pm 11.33
		Nymphs-3	11.03 \pm 4.17	2.54 \pm 2.40
	Moulting (%)	Nymphs-3	91.16 \pm 10.47	92.21 \pm 6.84
	Oviposition (n° eggs/female)	Females	228.91 \pm 13.04	192.73 \pm 41.52
	Viability of eggs (%)	Eggs	94.97 \pm 3.08	90.21 \pm 2.73
	<i>Ornithodoros erraticus</i>	Ingested blood (mg)	Males	3.36 \pm 0.07
Females			9.39 \pm 0.92	11.12 \pm 0.27
Nymphs-3			2.60 \pm 0.62	2.50 \pm 0.17
Mortality (%)		Males	1.15 \pm 1.99	0
		Females	0	0
		Nymphs-3	0.78 \pm 1.04	4.94 \pm 1.85
Moulting (%)		Nymphs-3	95.96 \pm 3.51	88.5 \pm 5.89
Oviposition (n° eggs/female)		Females	31.72 \pm 30.60	33.73 \pm 7.05
Viability of eggs (%)		Eggs	88.61 \pm 29.37	93.74 \pm 5.00

on acquiring cholesterol from the diet (Clark and Block, 1959; Voght et al., 2007). This feature can be exploited for design strategies for controlling tick infestations.

The analysis of the mialomes of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* retrieved several transcripts annotated as “Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing protein” whose expression level was significantly increased at 48 h post-feeding. This expression dynamics suggested that these transcripts could be important for *Ornithodoros* ticks during their initial phases of blood digestion (Oleaga et al., 2015, 2017b). Since this hypothesis makes these proteins interesting potential targets for anti-tick vaccines, the aim of this work has been the molecular and functional characterization of Niemann-Pick type C1 domain-containing proteins of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* including the evaluation of their protective potential in animal vaccine trials.

The cloning, sequencing, and analysis of OmNPC1 and OeNPC1 show that both sequences correspond to the conserved Niemann-Pick C1 N-terminus domain. This domain is analogous to the N-terminus of cholesterol transporter molecules, NPC1L1(NTD), and NPC1(NTD), expressed in other invertebrates (Hayakawa et al., 2021; Bolaños et al., 2016) and mammals (Kwon et al., 2009, 2011). This domain harbours the cholesterol binding pocket involved in the uptake and transport of cholesterol. Given that these proteins are highly conserved molecules in eukaryotes organisms (Winkler et al., 2022; Bolaños et al., 2016), it

could be assumed that OmNPC1 and OeNPC1, expressed in the midgut of *Ornithodoros* ticks, may be involved in the uptake and transport the dietary cholesterol inside enterocytes.

RNAi-mediated gene knockdown is a widely used technique for functional analysis of target genes. In this study, we conducted an RNAi assay wherein females from both species were administered dsRNA_OeNPC1 or dsRNA_OmNPC1. In *O. moubata*, a 51.8 % knockdown of the OmNPC1 gene was achieved, resulting in a significant decrease in the percentage of viable eggs in treated females without affecting the other parameters analysed. Conversely, in *O. erraticus*, OeNPC1 gene knockdown did not affect the treated ticks, despite OeNPC1 mRNA expression level was reduced by up to 66.6 %. This absence of a phenotypic effect could be explained by the presence of additional intestinal molecules with equivalent or overlapping functions. Therefore, the loss of function induced by RNAi could have been compensated by other receptors with similar functions. In this regard, it is described that both human NPC1L1 and low-density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR) mediate cholesterol uptake from extracellular sources through the clathrin-dependent pathway. LDLR is responsible for acquiring cholesterol in the form of low-density lipoproteins from the blood, whereas NPC1L1 receives unesterified cholesterol from the intestinal lumen and liver canalicular space (Luo et al., 2020). In the *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* mialomes, several transcripts annotated as “low-density lipoprotein receptor” have been found upregulated at 48 h post-feeding (Oleaga et al., 2015, 2017b). Taking these data into account, we cannot discard the possibility that the loss of function induced by OeNPC1 and OmNPC1 gene knockdown is being compensated for by intestinal LDLRs with overlapping functions. An additional explanation for the absence of significant phenotypic effects in the RNAi study could be the presence of pre-synthesised NPC1 in the tick tissues before the dsRNA-mediated gene knockdown. The western blot in Fig. 7, which shows the expression of the native OmNPC1 protein in the midgut extracts of *O. moubata*, supports this notion.

Regarding potential off-target effects, the analysis of the physiological parameters in control ticks treated with an unrelated dsRNA (dsRNA_Luc) or with injection buffer alone does not support their occurrence.

Given that cholesterol is involved in key physiological processes in ticks, it can be supposed that the addition of cholesterol metabolism inhibitors to the tick blood meal could affect tick fitness. This is the reason why we wanted to analyse the effect on tick physiology of inhibiting cholesterol absorption by NPC1 using EZT. The results of in vitro feeding of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* males, females, and nymphs-3 on blood supplemented with 10 μ g/ml EZT showed high mortality rates (approximately 70 %) in *O. moubata* adults, without affecting any other parameter in any other developmental stages of this species. Unexpectedly, this effect was not observed in *O. erraticus*, whose parameters remained unaffected by feeding on EZT-treated blood. The reason behind this difference is unknown, but it could be related to particular anatomical-physiological differences between both species, such as the lack of an anatomical connection between the midgut and the rectal ampoule in *O. moubata* (Soneshine and Roe, 2014). Moreover, consistent with the findings reported by Xavier et al. (2021), we could not test higher concentrations of EZT due to the toxic effect of the DMSO solvent. Considering the limited solubility of EZT, an increase in its concentration requires a higher proportion of DMSO.

The significant reduction in the number of fertile eggs caused by the OmNPC1 gene knockdown, along with the high mortality in male and female *O. moubata* fed on blood with EZT, led us to test the ability of recombinant tOmNPC1 to elicit protective immune responses in a vaccination trial in rabbits. To our knowledge, no component of the Niemann-Pick C1 family has been tested as a vaccine antigen target prior this study.

With this objective in mind, we initially demonstrated that the tOmNPC1 recombinant was highly immunogenic and elicited robust humoral responses in all vaccinated animals. The immune sera exhibited

slight reactivity to midgut protein extracts in ELISA, but they clearly identified, in western blotting (Fig. 7), the native OmNPC1 protein in the midgut extracts of *O. moubata*. These immune sera displayed a stronger reaction to the midgut extract from unfed females, suggesting a higher abundance of the protein in this physiological condition. This finding appears to contradict the higher expression of its encoding mRNA observed in the transcriptome analysis of fed females (Oleaga et al., 2017b). However, these results are not truly contradictory, as the correlation between mRNA and protein expressions can generally be low due to various factors, including the different half-lives of proteins and post-transcriptional machinery (Haider and Pal, 2013).

Contrary to expectations, the anti-OmNPC1 antibodies induced in rabbits had no negative effect on either species. Specifically, in *O. erraticus* this outcome may not be as surprising since, according to the western blot results, the anti-OmNPC1 antibodies did not recognize the native OeNPC1 in the *O. erraticus* midgut accounting for the lack of effect (Fig. 7). However, the lack of protective effect to *O. moubata*, despite the high level of anti-OmNPC1 antibodies was unexpected. Two potential reasons may be behind this result: (i) OmNPC1 may be an intracellular protein little accessible to antibodies. In this regard, human NPC1L1(NTD) and NPC1(NTD) are located, respectively, in the plasma membrane and lysosomes of enterocytes. Hence, there is a possibility that OmNPC1 is not expressed in the outer membrane of enterocytes in contact with ingested blood, as human NPC1L1(NTD), but rather is a lysosomal protein involved in the intracellular regulation of cholesterol metabolism, as the human NPC1(NTD) (Infante et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2011; Li et al., 2016).. (ii) We think it would be highly probable that other receptors involved in the uptake and transport of dietary cholesterol in midgut, such as the LDLRs identified in the midgut of *O. moubata*, may have compensated for the loss of function of OmNPC1 induced by the vaccine (Oleaga et al., 2017b; Luo et al., 2020). If so, designing a multi-antigen vaccine that includes both types of transporters could prove to be a highly promising strategy (Ndawula and Tabor, 2020).

Further detailed studies on OmNPC1 tissue expression and multi-antigenic vaccine assays including several cholesterol receptors, are required to shed light on these points.

5. Conclusions

This study explores the hypothesis that tick viability could be affected by interfering with cholesterol metabolism. Our data demonstrate a reduction in egg viability caused by gene knockdown of the OmNPC1 and high mortality in adult *O. moubata* fed on blood with EZT. To our knowledge, this study provides the first molecular and functional data of a Niemann-Pick type protein in soft ticks and shows that impaired cholesterol metabolism causes detrimental effects on the parasite. Considering these results and according to Maritz-Olivier et al (2023), we believe that targeting cholesterol metabolism, specifically the Niemann-Pick type protein(s), represents a promising approach for developing drug or vaccine targets to control tick populations.

Animal welfare statement

The procedures for tick feeding and experimentation with rabbits received approval by the Ethical and Animal Welfare Committee of the Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiología (IRNASA) and the Ethical Committee of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC, Spain) (Permit number 742/2017).

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve spelling, grammar, and general editing of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lucía de Dios-Blázquez: Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Ana Laura Cano-Argüelles:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Ricardo Pérez-Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **María González-Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ana Oleaga:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ttbdis.2024.102382](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ttbdis.2024.102382).

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